

Role of Social Media on Mental Well-being of Youth during Covid-19

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ABSTRACT

With COVID-19 spreading quickly, the world is moving into a new phase. People will be researching different COVID-19 pandemic effects, and mental and behavioral health should be the primary concern of such research. There is an abundance of research on the connection between emergencies like SARS or natural disasters and problems with loneliness, acute stress, anxiety, and depression. The COVID-19 pandemic's social isolation features may have particularly substantial effects on mental health, future prevention and treatment plans will be influenced by an understanding of how mental health changes as a result of this serious worldwide pandemic.

Keywords: Covid-19, Lockdown, Stress, Social media, Mental health

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I. INTRODUCTION

The current global coronavirus disease pandemic known as COVID-19 is also referred to as the coronavirus pandemic. In December 2019, a new virus was discovered during a pandemic in the Chinese city of Wuhan. On January 30, 2020, and March 11, 2020, accordingly, the World Health Organization (WHO) labeled the outbreak a pandemic and a public health emergency of worldwide concern. The pandemic was one of the deadliest in history as of 30 April 2023, with 764,473,623 diagnoses and 6,915,273 verified deaths. To stop the virus's spread, COVID-19 immunization and other preventive measures were implemented (Longest & Kang, 2022). Novel antiviral medicines and symptom management are used as treatments. Travel restrictions, lockdowns, business restrictions and closures, workplace hazard controls, quarantines, testing systems, and contact tracing of the infected are just a few of the public health mitigation measures that, when combined with treatments, help to control and eventually end the pandemic.

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Symptoms of COVID-19 are variable, ranging from mild symptoms to severe illness. Common symptoms include headache, loss of smell and taste, nasal congestion and runny nose, cough, muscle pain, sore throat, fever, diarrhea, and breathing difficulties (Debnath, 2004).

Many nations and regions imposed quarantines, entry bans, or other restrictions as a result of the pandemic, either for their citizens, travelers who had recently visited affected areas, or for all travelers. The pandemic and its responses to it damaged the global economy hundreds of millions of jobs were lost. The business was at a loss even though some got permanently shut down, panic buying of goods in bundles and stocks due to the lockdown, and supply. Some areas even witnessed a sharp increase in food prices due to the lockdown. Numerous countries' educational institutions were impacted by the pandemic. Many governments temporarily shut down educational facilities, which were frequently replaced by online learning the effects of school closures on kids, teachers, and families have significant negative societal and economic effects, problems like unavailability of smartphones, expensive data charges, mobile network issues, single mobile for one whole family. Some research works claimed that the pandemic has caused a huge impact on the mental health of students, anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic disorder, even affecting healthcare workers, patients, and quarantined individuals.

During the lockdown, people began spending a significant amount of time on social media, and social media has become a major component of life for many young people today. Whether positive or negative, most people use social media without considering the consequences on their lives. Social media is an ideal platform for swiftly disseminating content around the world, with pieces like "breaking news" receiving hundreds of thousands of comments. Although social media has a good impact on people, it also has an adverse impact on people. Some positive aspects are connection, healthy feedback, marketing, reducing social stigma, collaboration, openness, easy access, etc., while some negative aspects are cyber bullying, isolation, distraction, etc.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

(Chan, Nickson, Rudolph, Lee, & Joynt, 2020) If used responsibly and effectively, social media has the ability to offer quick and efficient channels for disseminating crucial information in the person's perspective of the methods via which others in their supporting social network, such as family, friends, or coworkers, might help them is known as social support. Through sharing personal stories and coping mechanisms for dealing with the day-to-day problems of living with a mental illness, people with serious mental illness report benefits from interacting with peers online. These benefits include increased social connectedness and feelings of group membership. Serious mental illness sufferers should fight stigma in online forums by emancipating themselves and offering hope.

(Lund, Aschbrenner, Marsch, & J., 2016)-One of the main motivations for connecting with others online, according to young adults with mental illness, is to feel less alone. Popular social media platforms help those with severe mental illnesses feel connected and relieved to know that others go through the same struggles. Additionally, research indicates that since online networks can be

anonymous, it is easier for people to express their actual selves there without fear of rejection or making mistakes.

(Shensa, et al., 2020)-found that emotional support obtained from social media differs from face-to-face emotional support that decreases the risk of depression in young adults; social-media-oriented emotional support increases the risk of depression.

(Serafini, et al., 2020)The role of online social support becomes crucial to increasing the likelihood of reducing psychological distress during the outbreak of COVID-19 (Longest & Kang, 2022)-The current study examines how COVID-19 has affected young adults' mental health in the US and how they use social media to maintain their social networks and manage the stress brought on by the pandemic. For those who are unable to find sufficient social support groups offline, social media has been seen as a viable method for boosting social support. and the amount of time spent on social media use was not associated with depression symptoms.

(Hunsinger & Theresa Senft, 2014) -Social media has been praised for encouraging increased participation in and inventiveness with cultural practices. According to reports, the creation of a free culture where people are empowered to participate in cultural production utilizing raw materials like home films and characters from popular television has been attributed to social media sites like Twitter and YouTube. Civic involvement and entertaining, imaginative political activism are made possible by this meme culture.

(Nowland, Necka, & Cassioppo, 2018)It has been suggested that social media may be a source of social connection and inclusion in regard to loneliness and mental health, which may prevent or alleviate loneliness.

(Geirdal, et al., 2021)According to the research evaluation, social media use is broad, and there are complex relationships between social media use and its effects on different groups of people. The frequency of using social media within a certain time period and more precise measurements like the number of minutes or hours spent on social media over a normal day are both common ways to estimate how much time people spend using social media.

(Chukwuere, 2022)Social media outlets are critical in supporting the public in staying informed and up to date on the COVID-19 epidemic. The public also relies on social media to gather information and understand the outbreak, symptoms, control and management, and containment measures supplied by authorized public and commercial healthcare companies.

III. OBJECTIVES

The study tried to find answers to the following research questions:

- What was the impact of using social media on stress?
- What was the impact of social media on social support during lockdown?
- Does the use of social media increase anxiety in people during this lockdown?

Based on the above, the study objectives are:

- To study the role of social media on the well-being of youth during the covid-19 lockdown
- To understand the proclivity of youth towards the media during lockdown

IV. DATA AND METHODS

The study is based on descriptive research design as it will only describe the mental feeling, condition or state of youth by the use of social media during lockdown. The study is quantitative in nature. Purposive random sampling has been used to select 100 sample units from two districts, Shahdol and Annupur. Data was collected from the 100 respondents through online mode by using online questionnaire (with closed ended questions) through google form. The 100 respondents were in the age group 20 years to 30 years; both males and females were in an equal ratio. 70% of the respondents were students and 30% were employed in full-time and part-time jobs.

V. ANALYSIS

80% of the respondents felt connected with people around them by using social media. The most used application for social connectivity was WhatsApp, one of the primary application found almost in every smartphone, followed by Instagram and Facebook. People expressed that with the use of social media they are able to connect with each other at any time which makes them feel less lonely.

Figure 1: Overall Mental Health

Source: Primary Data from Survey

Figure-2: Feeling Depressed

Source: Primary Data from Survey

Figure-3: Average Hours Spent on Social Media per Day

Source: Primary Data from Survey

Figure-4: Experience of the Respondents While Using Social Media

Source: Primary Data from Survey

Figure-5: Respondents Ever Diagnosed with Mental Disorder

Source: Primary Data from Survey

Figure-6: Sleep Duration of Participants during Covid-19

Source: Primary Data from Survey

Figure-7: Quality of Sleep during Lockdown

Source: Primary Data from Survey

Figure-8: Relationship of Respondents with their Family during Lockdown

Source: Primary Data from Survey

Figure-9: Social Media and its Use to Gather Update on Covid-19

Source: Primary Data from Survey

Figure-10: Trust Level of Respondents on Different Social Media Apps for News Updates

Source: Primary Data from Survey

Figure-11: Percentage of Respondents Who Felt Socially Connected by Using Social Media

Source: Primary Data from Survey

Figure-12: Percentage of Respondents Watching Different Content

Source: Primary Data from Survey

Figure-13: Application Used by the Respondents for Communication

Source: Primary Data from Survey

VI. CONCLUSION

Social media has helped people to feel entertained in their leisure time and to get involved in different activities from their residences without going outdoors. Through regular contact by using simple and easy social media tools or apps people were able to share their views, information, ideas, and thoughts with the people they want especially feeling connected with their family through regular calls, Facetime, and instant messages with pop-up sound on the mobile screen by messenger app were giving smiles to the peoples. Social media have also helped people to search for jobs and other online startups to start generating income online through different mediums like LinkedIn for freelancing, YouTube for content creation, and online teaching apps for teaching, the dependency on the internet and social networkingsite can easily be understand during lockdown how the corporate jobs shifted to work from home, the growth of online market, online training (gym, parlors, painting etc.) the growth of online educating institution, we can see the fast growth in numbers as well the reach of YouTube channels. Social media has helped people to stay in good mental condition by providing different stages to get entertained, connected, and work on a daily basis.

VII. REFERENCES

- Chan, A. K., Nickson, C., Rudolph, J. W., Lee, A., & Joynt, G. M. (2020). Social Media For Rapid Knowledge Dissemination: Early Experience From The COVID-19 Pandemic. *PubMed Central*, 1579-1582. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m1554>
- Chukwuere, J. (2022). Social media and COVID-19 pandemic: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of African Films, Diaspora Studies, Performance Arts and Communication Studies*.
- Debnath, D. (2004). The Health Problems and Status of the Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups of Madhya Pradesh: A Case Study in Anthropological Dimension. *Man In India*. [Volume and page numbers unavailable].

- Geirdal, A., Ruffolo, M., Leung, J., Thygesen, H., Price, D., Bonsaksen, T., & Schoultz, M. (2021). Mental Health, Quality of Life, Wellbeing, Loneliness, and Use of Social Media in a Time of Social Distancing During the COVID-19 Outbreak: A Cross-Country Comparative Study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(3), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18031028>
- Hunsinger, J., & Senft, T. (2014). *The social media handbook*. Routledge/Taylor & Francis Group.
- Longest, K., & Kang, J. A. (2022). Social Media, Social Support, and Mental Health of Young Adults During COVID-19. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.825423>
- Lund, J. A., Aschbrenner, K. A., Marsch, L. A., & S. B., J. (2016). The Future of Mental Health Care: Peer-to-Peer Support and Social Media. *Cambridge University Press*. [Book, no volume/issue numbers].
- Naslund, J. A., Aschbrenner, K. A., Marsch, L. A., & Bartels, S. J. (2016). The Future of Mental Health Care: Peer-to-Peer Support and Social Media. *Psychiatric Services*, 67(3), 365-367. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ps.201500229>
- Nowland, R., Necka, E., & Cacioppo, J. (2018). Loneliness and Social Internet Use: Pathways to Reconnection in a Digital World? *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 13(1), 7-23. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691617713052>
- Serafini, G., Parmigiani, B., Amerio, A., Aguglia, A., Sher, L., & Amore, M. (2020). The Psychological Impact of COVID-19 on the Mental Health in the General Population. *QJM: An International Journal of Medicine*, 113(8), 531-537. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qjmed/hcaa207>
- Shensa, A., Sidani, J. E., Viera, C. G., Switzer, G. E., Primack, B. A., & Bradley, S. C. (2020). Emotional Support From Social Media and Face-to-Face Relationships: Associations with Depression Risk Among Young Adults. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 23(1), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cyber.2019.0392>

